

The Promise and the Paradox of Law: Gendered Violence against Women and the Limits of Legal Remedies in India

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Abstract: Gender-based violence has been prevalent in Indian society since time immemorial. Women generally encounter violence from the very inception of the fetus in the mother's womb. Indian society presents a paradoxical scenario, as women are worshipped as goddesses and at the same time subjected to various forms of crime at different phases of life. This anomaly is often addressed by setting moral standards and promoting religious teachings. However, the available facts demonstrate the inadequacy of traditional methods to minimize such violence. The state has taken a number of steps in the form of introducing social legislation to curb the menace of gender-based violence, especially to protect women in a society still dictated by patriarchal values. Women not only face violence outside their homes but are also exposed to various forms of violence within the four walls of their homes, based on existing power relations. The changing laws and their interpretations by the judiciary are evidence of initiatives to address the issue of gendered violence in contemporary society. The enacted laws are a manifestation of efforts to fulfill the expectations of all women, irrespective of their social status, to live a life free from any form of violence and to achieve gender equality in the truest sense. This article is based on secondary sources and seeks to highlight the laws as tools for the protection of Indian women, along with the grey areas where the deficiencies and inadequacies of existing laws are still felt.

Key Words: Gendered Violence, Legislations, Justice, Discrimination

Understanding Gendered Violence in India: Social Roots and Legal Responses

Gendered violence denotes the harmful acts that affect victims in every society. A closer look reveals that in the majority of cases, women become the victims. The societal hierarchies constructed on the basis of gender have given rise to inequalities and discrimination across the world, especially in Latin American countries, African nations, and Asia (Bandopadhyaya, 2020). The coexistence of men and women within a society marked by violence often does not draw immediate attention due to the normalization of such violence and the pervasive culture of silence on the part of women. In fact, the root of this violence lies buried in the very structures and interactions that constitute a society.

The categorization of men and women ultimately leads to the assignment of superiority and inferiority to men and women, respectively. This gendered division favours men and exposes women to violence, injustice, and exclusion from the true enjoyment of freedom. The root cause of gendered violence in any society lies within the family unit, which serves as the primary site of socialization. This family unit becomes a breeding ground for unequal power relations between men and women. The persistent existence of harmful societal norms and practices gives men an upper hand. In order to maintain supremacy and exercise authority over women, men often resort to abusive acts and behaviours.

It is not surprising that Indian women are exposed to various forms of violence, including female feticide, infanticide, honour killings, dowry deaths, moles-

tation, rape, child marriage, and domestic violence. History shows that gender-based violence is among the most underreported and ignored human rights violations, as it is often considered a natural phenomenon. Indian women, who are socialized to practise tolerance and silence, are subjected to untold miseries and hardships arising from the atrocities committed by men (Reddy, 2021). It is argued that the inequality experienced by women starts at birth, when Hindu society celebrates the birth of a male child. This male child is raised with the false belief that he is entitled to certain privileges, including control over women. Yet Hindu scriptures portray man and woman as two aspects of one being. In fact, these scriptures propagate that women are more powerful than men and are to be treated as goddesses of “*Shakthi*” (Power) (Myneni, 2002). However, in reality, one can see that women face numerous difficulties due to the violence meted out to them daily. This violence renders women victims who are deprived of dignity, equality, and equity in society. Even in the twenty-first century, women are married off early to guarantee chastity, female fetuses are aborted, spousal rapes are overlooked, and domestic violence is used to control women within families. While the world is pursuing gender equality and has set it as a Sustainable Development Goal to be achieved by 2030, its primary requirement which is freeing women from violence, remains elusive in Indian society.

It is true that the Indian state is not sitting idle. The Indian Parliament has passed numerous pieces of legislation to minimize and eliminate gender-based violence. The Indian judiciary,

Through proactive interpretation of laws and praise worthy initiatives such as issuing guidelines in the absence of specific legislation, also seeks to protect Indian women from violence. It is undeniable that existing laws serve as facilitators in achieving gender equality and equity. Yet innumerable reports show that women continue to suffer mental agony, anxiety, bodily violations, and other harms due to violence committed by men. In the name of maintaining general moral standards, men often impose certain barriers that amount to violence in disguise. Such violence results in the non-fulfilment of women’s potential and the continued existence of unreasonable oppression, social ills, and the absence of free will in both the private and public spheres of Indian society. This article is an attempt to present a true picture of the effectiveness of Indian laws in addressing the violence encountered by women in Indian society.

Methodology:

This article is based on secondary data. The secondary data sources include published books, bare Acts, academic journals, newspapers, official reports, and other relevant documents.

Legal Protection against Gender-based violence:

Gender-based violence has been recognised in various laws, as it is considered a direct onslaught on the right to life with dignity, as enshrined in the Indian Constitution. It is an established fact that the roots of violence are embedded in the gender culture practised in Indian society. It should be noted that the redressal of violence against women lies in a proper understanding of gender, which manifests in a complex and largely unwritten set of rules that mould human behaviour (Ekins & King, 2006).

Laws in Indian society have acknowledged the notion of gender inequality, unequal gender relations, stereotypes, and the imbalance of power between men and women in order to bring justice to women. The framers of the Indian Constitu-

tion were well aware of the situation of women, and they incorporated protective provisions under Part III of the Constitution, which deals with the fundamental rights available to all citizens. This bold step was remarkable against the backdrop of the deeply entrenched masculine features of Indian society. The tolerance of violence on the part of women can be attributed to the prevailing, systematically biased prescriptive norms that women are expected to follow (Mishra & Salve, 2023). Indian women are typically norm-internalising rather than resorting to rule-defying behaviours. This tendency proves to be a barrier for legislation to effectively address many forms of violence that occur in both the private and public domains. Laws do not automatically bring about changes in the masculine or feminine behaviours of men and women, but they can act as catalysts for change and serve as deterrents. The passing of relevant legislation paves the way for women to gain gender equality, which was a cherished aspiration of the framers of the Indian Constitution. The Fundamental Duties, incorporated by the 42nd Amendment to the Indian Constitution, also impose an obligation on Indian citizens to renounce derogatory practices against women (Kumar, 2020). However, it must be remembered that this duty is not mandatory, and hence men who resort to violence cannot be punished by the court merely for violating this Fundamental Duty.

This indirectly encourages men to indulge in reckless acts against women. Laws in India have been formulated to address issues of violence that directly or indirectly affect the physical, emotional, and psychological well-being of women.

It is pertinent to examine the legislation relating to the family set-up, which marks the beginning of life's journey for every individual, irrespective of gender. Many marriage-related and civil laws have been enacted to preserve the rights of women, but the Indian State was somewhat reluctant to directly address the issue of domestic violence, also known as intimate partner violence, due to the normative structure of Indian society. The consistent engagement and sustained efforts of women's organisations, lawyers' collectives, and public-spirited individuals ultimately compelled the government to introduce a significant law: *The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005*, which aims to protect Indian women within the four walls of their homes. Even though Section 498A was introduced into the Indian Penal Code, it is now replaced by Section 85 of *The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita*, to deal with cruelty faced by women at the hands of husbands or their relatives, it was unable to address the phenomenon of domestic violence in its entirety. The enactment of the 2005 Act was a watershed moment in Indian legal history, as it also recognised the concerns of women in live-in relationships, who were previously invisible in the eyes of the law. This legislation, in fact, empowered women who are in relationships outside marriage to seek redress for the violence they face (Nair, 2011). Another area of concern for women since time immemorial is the issue of rape. This is one of the most heinous crimes in the world committed against women. Patriarchal values have made women's sexuality a site of exploitation and control. The Indian Penal Code categorically states in Section 375 that rape involves coercive sexual intercourse where there is no consent or where it is committed against the will of the woman. This offence is severely punishable with imprisonment for life or rigorous imprisonment for a term not less than twenty years, or with the death penalty (Reddy, 2021).

The Indian Penal Code also considers the issue of the rape of a wife during separation. However, the same Indian law remains silent in the context of marital rape of adult women within the institution of marriage. The false cultural notion

that women must surrender to the will of their husbands for the gratification of sexual desires and the preservation of marital sanctity fuels unwanted physical intimacy, which can take the form of forceful rape, battering rape, and obsessive rape by husbands. It is an unfortunate reality that reliable data on marital rape are still unavailable, largely due to the lackadaisical attitude of the government towards this issue. This form of violence has a profound impact on the psychological health of women. It is deeply troubling that women who are violated in this way must continue to share their lives, families, and children with the perpetrator of such violence, which ultimately creates a profound trust deficit within marriage (Chowdhury, 2022). The legal acceptance of conjugal rights, without taking into consideration issues of excessive and unreasonable demands for sex or unnatural sex within the institution of marriage, jeopardises the rights of married women in Indian society. It is true that women can approach the court for divorce on the ground so fun acceptable forms of sexual emands made by their husbands. However, this is a civil remedy, not a criminal one (Singh, 2009).

Another grey area that existed in law has been addressed by The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023 is protection of women from sexual intercourse by employing deceitful means. It was seen in the past that thousands of women were deceived by men to share intimacy with the expectation of marriage/ promotion in future which proved to be an elusive dream and any legal protection. This deceitful act is now recognized as a crime not amounting to the offence of rape under Section-69 of The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023 and made punishable to imprisonment. This new Section is expected to prevent and protect women from sexual exploitation and break the culture of silence.

Another form of gender-based violence is dowry. Reports of dowry deaths are still very common on television, in newspaper coverage, and on social media. Recognising this social evil, lawmakers enacted *The Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961*. However, this is one of the most ineffective pieces of legislation, as it has miserably failed to protect women from violence. Dowry is deeply rooted in Indian society and is widely accepted as an inviolable social custom at the time of marriage by all sections of society. This mindset complicates the implementation of the Act, which prohibits the giving or taking of dowry and makes it a punishable offence. The social complexity and stigma often prevent parents from invoking this particular law and seeking legal recourse (Reddy, 2021). This uncontrollable dowry system has negative consequences, such as sex selection of the child. Violence is inflicted upon the female fetus even before birth. The advancement of technology in the medical field is also being misused to perpetrate violence against the female fetus in the early stages of pregnancy. The introduction of the *Pre-Natal Diagnostic Techniques (Regulation and Prevention of Misuse) Act, 1994* bears testimony to the mischief committed in this regard. The misuse of diagnostic techniques in the pursuit of achieving a masculine sex ratio has resulted in millions of abortions of female fetuses in India. The invisible trauma of Indian women who have been forced to undergo such abortions remains largely undocumented.

Sometimes, the law itself can be indirectly blamed for the subjugation of women. Section 497 of the recently repealed Indian Penal Code dealt with the issue of adultery and considered it a crime. A five-judge Constitution Bench led by the then Chief Justice Mr. Dipak Misra struck down this colonial-era law to liberate women from a subordinate position and to uphold their dignity and sexual autonomy. It was observed by one of the judges that this section was based on gender

stereotypes and was aimed at preventing women from exercising their sexual agency. This judgment marked the end of an era in which a husband could claim ownership over the sexuality of his wife. This judicial decision was, in fact, a step in the right direction (Kumar S., 2018).

Other forms of violence faced by women, which are addressed under *The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023*, may also be mentioned in this context. Crimes such as murder, culpable homicide, hurt, grievous hurt, causing miscarriage, kidnapping, abduction, procurement of minor girls, importation of girls from foreign countries, selling minors for the purposes of prostitution, buying minors for the purposes of prostitution, sexual intercourse by a person in authority, gang rape, and others have all been made punishable under *The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023*. In addition, several special laws, such as *The Medical Termination of Pregnancy Act, 1971*, *The Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, 2006*, and *The Immoral Traffic (Prevention) Act, 1956*, are also being enforced to protect women from various forms of violence.

Emerging new forms of Violence and Legal Response:

It is undeniable that Indian society is changing at a faster pace than ever before. New forms of violence are also emerging, which require innovative legal responses. Some of these acts of violence are perpetrated behind the façade of the cyber world. Crimes such as acid attacks have created considerable concern, as they aim to leave the victim in a pathetic condition for the rest of their life (Reddy, 2021). The alarming fact is that this crime is grossly underestimated and often ignored in common parlance. Section 124 of *The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023* incorporates the offence of voluntarily causing grievous hurt by use of acid and makes it a cognizable and non-bailable offence. Another emerging form of violence is voyeurism, which is a cybercrime intended to destroy personal privacy and dignity by video recording or photographing unsuspecting individuals. Section 66E of the *Information Technology Act, 2000* addresses this crime and seeks to punish the “Peeping Toms” who intrude upon the privacy of women. Similarly, Section 78 of *The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023* has been incorporated to deal with the issue of stalking. The majority of stalking victims are women, and this crime is often committed in the cyber world by monitoring women’s use of the internet and making repeated attempts to contact them despite their clear expression of disinterest. A similar type of violence is faced by millions of women in their workplaces: sexual harassment. The increasing involvement of women in different forms of employment around the clock exposes them to this crime. The need to harness the intellectual capabilities of women in all sectors also necessitates adequate protective measures. The landmark judgment pronounced by the Supreme Court of India in *Vishaka v. State of Rajasthan*, AIR 1997SC 3011, drew critical attention to the issue of sexual harassment faced by women at the workplace. As a result, the Government of India was compelled to enact *The Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013*, which imposes an obligation on employers to ensure the prevention, prohibition, and redressal of sexual harassment at work (Kumar G, 2014).

Conclusion:

The subject of violence against women is not new, and the constant efforts by the Government to address it through the enactment of new laws are also a time-tested mechanism. However, it must be remembered that legislation alone cannot be expected to address this issue. Despite numerous existing laws, the increasing

rate of violence against women indicates that something is missing in the system. Perpetrators know that their actions result in the suffering and loss of women's dignity and rights. Yet they continue to commit such acts because they are aware that the system is fragile and often partial. There is a clear absence of the political will required for the effective implementation of laws in their true spirit. Indian society is well known for its knee-jerk reactions whenever a brutal incident such as the *Nirbhaya* case, the *Hathras* incident, or the

R.G. Kar Hospital murder takes place. Yet the laws remain inactive or only partially active because the administration often fails to allow them to function effectively. There is every possibility that unless the politics of power which remains controlled by patriarchal interests is transformed, there will be little chance of genuinely mitigating violence against women.

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